

Validation of a sensory-motor prosthesis with integrated thermal feedback in a transradial amputee

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Abstract

Recent studies have opened new opportunities for Robotic Prosthetic Hand (RPH) users in terms of dexterity and effective sensory-motor control. Indeed, we can now glimpse a future where amputees could control and perceive their RPH as an intact hand. Here, we show that the natural thermal sensations (cold and hot) can be seamlessly integrated into commercially available RPHs using a noninvasive technology. Wearing this novel prototype, a transradial amputee could detect the thermal properties of different objects in real-time in several sensory-motor tasks. This study paves the way for more natural hand prostheses.

Introduction

Recently, we showed that it is possible to deliver natural thermal sensations over the full range of non-painful stimuli (15°C to 40°C) in upper limb amputees. We reported that the noninvasive thermal stimulation of specific spots of the residual arm can induce phantom thermal sensations¹. We found that these sensations are stable over time and similar to the ones experienced on the intact arm. Building upon these findings, we developed a portable device called the MiniTouch that conveys real-time temperature feedback.

Here, we show the integration of the MiniTouch with a commercial RPH; we call this integrated standalone system the *Thermal prosthetic hand*. We show how a transradial amputee successfully exploited the Thermal prosthetic hand during a series of active sensory-motor tasks involving grasping, pinching, and poking to discriminate objects with different temperatures and materials and detect bodily contact. We also introduce a novel assessment protocol — the thermal Box Block Test — which evaluates the prosthetic user's ability to exploit the phantom thermal sensations in a real-time functional task.

From thermal phantom sensations to the Thermal prosthetic hand

The subject (57-year-old male) has had a transradial amputation for 37 years with no phantom limb pain (VAS < 3); he participated in our previous study¹ (participant P12) and signed an informed consent form. The participant routinely used the MyoHand VariPlus (Ottobock, Germany). The procedure started with mapping the tactile and thermal phantom sensations using the thermal mapping protocol described by Iberite et al.¹ Using this protocol, we identified his thermal phantom hand maps, i.e., regions of the residual limb that can elicit thermal projected sensations.

Over the first 130 days, we performed four thermal mapping sessions; three points were consistently found to project into the phantom hand (see Fig. 1A). Then, on day 246, we selected one of these three stable points for the integration of the MiniTouch into the RPH; this point satisfied two critical conditions (a) its thermal projected sensation was stable (b) its location in the phantom hand map allowed the thermode to be placed without interfering with the EMG electrodes. We show in Fig 1B the placement of the thermode on the specific location on the phantom hand map and the sensor on the corresponding thermal projected spot on the prosthetic hand (index finger). Stable perpendicular contact of the thermode with the skin on the residuum was achieved by using an adjustable frame. Following the integration, the participant used the Thermal prosthetic hand to perform various motor tasks over eight experimental sessions between days 247 and 413. No further adjustments of the thermode position were necessary during these experiments as the participant confirmed that his thermal projected sensation was maintained constant. Furthermore, the subject reported no difficulty using the EMG signals in controlling the Thermal prosthetic hand throughout the sessions, and no adverse effects were reported during the experiments.

Sensory-motor tasks

We first investigated whether the participant could discriminate three objects with different temperatures by grasping them. The subject was instructed to close the Thermal prosthetic hand on a bottle containing either cold water, water at ambient temperature, or hot water. All bottles were visually similar (no condensation, steam, etc.), and the experiment started with a 1-minute familiarization where the labels cold (20°C), ambient (24°C), and hot (40°C) were described. Three conditions were repeated ten times in a randomized order. Confirming that the participant could perceive the thermal differences of grasped objects, he reached 100% accuracy — the same score as when he used his intact hand. In contrast, validating that he only relied on the thermal information to perform the task, his accuracy dropped to 33% when the thermal feedback was turned off (Fig. 2A).

To investigate the detection of more subtle thermal differences, we presented three slabs of materials at room temperature in a random order (five repetitions per material). We used a piece of copper, glass, and plastic for this task, as previously tested by our group in healthy² and amputee¹ populations. The participant (blindfolded) used the Thermal prosthetic hand to pinch the slabs, and he responded to a forced-choice questionnaire. The participant was correct in 67%

of the cases, with no confusion between the plastic and copper conditions; his accuracy rate was comparable to the one found when he used his intact arm to touch the objects (67%) (Fig. 2B). Once again when the thermal feedback was turned off, his accuracy did not exceed chance level.

While detecting objects' temperature and material is interesting to increase the catalog of thermal sensations for prosthetic users, an even more important aspect is to detect bodily sensations to potentially facilitate interactions with others. This was spontaneously reported several times by participants from our previous study. One participant said: "*The most impressive for me was when the experimenter placed the sensor on his own body. [...] I could feel the warmth of another person with my phantom hand. It [was] like having a connection with someone.*" To further investigate this crucial feature, we checked whether the participant (blindfolded) could discriminate a human arm from a prosthetic one by poking it. As a control, and because the compliance of a prosthetic hand could be different from a human hand, we also tested a softer silicone hand. We presented four conditions: two artificial arms (one prosthetic and one rubber arm) and two real arms (one female and one male subject). The participant poked the arm with his prosthetic hand for 5 seconds and reported whether it was a human arm or an artificial one. The participant detected correctly in 80% of the trials when the thermal feedback was On, a rate below the one reached with the intact hand (100%) but significantly above the chance level (chance level with $p < 0.05 = 70\%$ ³). The detection accuracy was 60% when the thermal feedback was off; therefore, while compliance might play some role in detecting the different artificial limbs, the thermal feedback boosted the detection accuracy (Fig. 2C).

Finally, we introduced a novel test to assess thermal feedback in a motor task. We based our assessment on the standard box and block test (BBT)⁴, where the participant has to move as many cubes as possible from one box to another in one minute.

Adding to the difficulty, in our test – called the thermal BBT – the cubes (made of stainless steel) were either cold (20°C) or hot (40°C), and the participant had to store them in a red (hot) or blue (cold) zone (Supplementary Movie S1). We repeated the thermal BBT 30 times: 15 with the thermal feedback On and 15 with the thermal feedback Off in a randomized order.

To confirm that the participant was familiar with the task and was able to move the blocks with the thermal prosthetic hand, we also performed 10 standard BBT sessions in standard conditions (cubes were at room temperature and thermal feedback was Off); participant was able to move between 23 and 32 cubes/minute. Comparatively, when considering the Thermal BBT task, the participant moved on average 10.2 ± 1.1 blocks/minute for the Feedback On and 13.9 ± 2.8 for the Feedback Off session (mean \pm SD). The decrease in the number of blocks in the thermal BBT compared to the standard BBT can be easily understood: the participant had to do a thermal discrimination task while performing the pick and place.

Crucially, when considering the feedback On session, we found that the participant correctly placed more than half of the blocks in *all* 15 sessions (min score = 64%). Overall, the participant correctly placed 114 out of 153 moved blocks. His error rates for hot and cold blocks were similar (22 errors over 76 hot blocks and 17 over 77 cold blocks). The participant was significantly worse at performing the task when the thermal feedback was Off (means accuracy for feedback On = 75%, feedback Off = 50%, $p < 0.001$, T-test). This test confirmed that the participant could perform a motor task with quick thermal discrimination. We believe the thermal BBT can become a benchmark test for the future development of RPH with thermal feedback.

Conclusion

We showed a novel sensory-motor prosthetic hand with integrated thermal feedback and its validation with a transradial amputee. Three important observations can be made: (a) the participant could control the Thermal prosthetic hand to actively explore objects to detect their thermal properties, (b) we found the presence of stable phantom thermal sensations in 413 days, (c) no adverse events were registered during any of the experiments. The participant's accuracy level when using the Thermal prosthetic hand to discriminate different objects' temperatures and materials was similar to the one with his intact hand. On the other hand, for the detection of bodily contact, while the presence of thermal feedback was found to improve the detection rate, it did not reach one of the intact hand, probably due to the lack of other multisensory information, such as skin texture.

Considering our previous finding that thermal phantom sensations are prevalent in upper limb amputees¹ and the rather simplicity of the Thermal prosthetic hand, which necessitates no surgical intervention, uses off-the-shelf electronics and can be personalized in just a few sessions, we believe our solution has the potential to become widespread for prosthetic users. Nevertheless, challenges lie ahead. First, further miniaturization of the controller and heat extraction module is necessary to integrate the thermal controller *inside* the socket (particularly challenging when the residual arm is long). Next, integrating multiple thermodes would be necessary for evoking larger parts of the phantom hand. Also, while no adverse effects were observed during both the current and our previous study¹, we need to carefully characterize the thermal feedback in all sorts of external conditions and its long-term effects.

But these challenges are worth the effort as the long-term use of the Thermal prosthetic hand could open completely new perspectives for prosthetic users. First, the participants could gather new sensations, such as wetness and richer bodily sensations. Second, for the first time, we can envision the possibility of restoring a multimodal palette of natural sensations integrating the thermal phantom sensations with tactile feedback via noninvasive⁵ or invasive⁶ interfaces. This could promote social interaction and affective touch^{7,8}; a particularly interesting implementation of such technology might be for bilateral amputees.

Third, while in the current work, we mainly concentrated on the active discrimination of thermal features of external objects, thermal feedback is also an interoceptive sensation: we can, for example, feel that our hands are cold or hot even when we touch nothing. An open question is how an interoceptive phantom thermal sensation influences RPH users' perception and how it could possibly boost their embodiment. Finally, knowing that integrating sensory feedback in RPH reduces phantom limb pain^{9,10}, we believe there is an opportunity for using thermal feedback to this end. Our case study shows the tremendous potential of the thermal prosthetic hand for clinical applications and opens the way for the investigation of the long-term term effects of thermal feedback on patients' quality of life.

Captions

Supplementary Movie S1. Thermal Box and Block Test. The participant uses the Thermal prosthetic hand to move and separate as many hot (40°C) and cold (20°C) metal cubes as possible in 60 seconds.

Authors contributions

Conceptualization: J.M., F.I., E.G., S.M. and S.S. Data collection: J.M., F.I., F.M. and S.S. Data analysis: J.M., F.I., S.M. and S.S. Development of the Thermal prosthetic hand: J.M., O.A., R.M., and S.S. Supervision: S.M. and S.S. Writing – original draft: J.M., F.I., S.M. and S.S. Writing – review & editing: All authors.

Competing interests:

S.M. holds shares in SensArs, which aims to develop bionic limbs for amputees. F.I., J.M., O.A., S.M., and S.S. are coinventors of a thermal sensing device and sensory feedback system and method using said thermal sensing device (application number EP22207038.5).

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Figures

A. Protocol timeline

B. System integration: the Thermal prosthetic hand

Figure 1. Integration of the thermal feedback system with a commercial RPH.

(A) Protocol timeline, including the thermal mapping of the residual arm and the experiments with the integrated Thermal prosthetic hand. A precise map of the residual arm was done using a thermode. We tested three temperatures: baseline skin temperature (32°C), below (25°C) and above (37°C) skin baseline. Three stable thermal projected spots were found between day one and day 130; among them, the blue point was chosen for integrating the MiniTouch with the RPH of the participant. The blue spot was then used between days 247 and 413 for a series of experiments with the Thermal prosthetic hand. During all these sessions, both skin baseline, below and above skin baseline stimulation elicited consistent thermal phantom sensations in the missing index finger. (B) The MiniTouch system integrates three main elements. (1) The Active Thermal Skin (ATS) sensor is a thin-film sensor integrating a heating track that stabilizes the sensor baseline temperature to 32°C and a sensing track monitoring the contact temperature. (2) The housing contains the system controller and a rechargeable battery. (3) The thermal display comprises a thermoelectric module, a temperature sensor, and a heatsink. It conveys the temperature of the ATS sensor on the thermal phantom spot. The support of the thermal display is mounted on screws ensuring that the thermode stays in tight contact with the skin. Top to down: the position of the projected thermal spots and the placement of the EMG sensors on the residual arm; the blue spot was selected as it did not interfere with the EMG electrodes. Square sections of the inner (2x2 cm²) and outer (4.2x4.2 cm²) sockets were carved to accommodate the thermode.

A. Temperature discrimination

B. Material discrimination

C. Bodily contact

D. Thermal Box and Blocks Test

Figure 2. Participant performance in sensory-motor tasks.

(A) Confusion matrices for three-class forced-choice identification of bottles of water with cold (20°C), ambient (24°C), or hot (40°C). (B) Confusion matrix for three-class forced-choice identification of copper, glass, or plastic slabs at ambient temperature (24°C). (C) Identification of artificial and human arms when poking a stiff prosthetic hand (PH), a soft rubber hand (RH), and two subjects' arms (S1 and S2). For panels (A) to (C), we report the scores when the participant used the thermal prosthetic hand with the thermal feedback On or Off and when he used the index finger of his non-amputated hand (intact index). (D) (Left) Confusion matrix (number of moved blocks over 15 sessions) and (Right) Classification accuracy (correctly placed blocks, mean ± SD) for the thermal BBT with the thermal feedback turned On or Off.